

THE ROLE OF UZBEKISTAN IN ENSURING SECURITY AND COOPERATION BETWEEN THE COUNTRIES OF CENTRAL ASIA

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the role of Uzbekistan in ensuring regional security and cooperation between Central Asian countries. Also, conclusions and suggestions were given on the importance of the role of Uzbekistan in ensuring regional security and cooperation in Central Asia.

In any society that has chosen the path of democratic development, along with the improvement of economic, social, cultural and spiritual foundations, the demand to raise political processes to a higher level is leading.

The political processes that determine the stable development of the state and society are directly related to the internal and external factors of this country. Until these factors gain socio-political importance and develop, the human phenomenon, its destiny, national interests, national and religious tolerance, inter-ethnic harmony and solidarity will remain in the whirlpool of one-sided or superficial views. In this sense, in the society of Uzbekistan, the development of regional issues, the development of mutual neighborly relations, recognition of the unity of values and interests towards a common goal, in the last five years, effective and comprehensive cooperation relations with the countries of Central Asia have been given a broad tone.

Uzbekistan is located at the intersection of civilizations, different cultural layers, different beliefs and worldviews. The Uzbek people, who make up the majority of the population, have played an important role in regional unity since ancient times. "Uzbekistan today is not only rich natural raw material reserves, unlimited market and investment area. At the moment, our country has enormous intellectual, spiritual and cultural potential. All this, in a situation where a new political and economic order is actively forming in the world, combined with the unique geographical location of our country, arouses great geo-political and geo-strategic interest" [1].

Uzbekistan, which is a pillar of peace and stability in Central Asia, geographical location in the region, economic potential, military capability, population, international reputation, and ancient traditions of statehood make it possible to fulfill these tasks. As noted by the experienced diplomat and scientist S. Safoev, "a set of factors such as geographical location,

economic potential, and population determine not only the position of Uzbekistan in the region, but also its special responsibility for this situation" [2].

Our country is independent in terms of raw materials and energy, and has many raw materials necessary for the consumer market. From the first years of independence, the government of Uzbekistan tried to be independent in terms of raw materials and energy resources. By 1998, production of oil and gas condensate increased 3 times compared to 1990. Our country has gained independence. If in 1990 more than 90 percent of wheat consumed in the republic was imported, in 1998 the share of imports was less than 19 percent. The volume of grain production increased by 3.7 times from 1899 thousand tons in 1990 to 6952 thousand tons in 2010. In 2014, our grain growers delivered more than 8,000 tons of grain. Today, Uzbekistan supplies grain to neighboring countries, even to Afghanistan. During 2000-2010, the growth of all types of agricultural products was achieved. Over the past period, the volume of grain production increased by 197.1%, vegetables by 235.1%, dairy products by 276.4%, fruit by 214.5%, meat production by 291.2%, milk by 169.8%, egg production by 243.8%.

Our country ranks fourth in the world in terms of cotton fiber delivery, and second in sales to the world market. In Central Asia, an average of 2 million tons of cotton fiber is grown per year, while Uzbekistan's share is 1 million 400 thousand tons. Uzbekistan is the only country in the region that produces silk and cocooning equipment. The Republic produces about 70,000 tons of cocoons per year, 21 tons of which are processed in our enterprises, and the rest are exported. Uzbekistan ranks seventh in the world in terms of gold mining and fourth in terms of reserves [3]. Kyzylkum and Muruntauv gold mines in our republic are among the largest mines in the world. There are more than 160 oil fields in the territory of our country with proven oil reserves of more than 4 billion tons. Condensed gas reserves are 630 billion tons, natural gas reserves are 5.5 trillion m³. Discovered coal reserves are more than 2 billion tons. More than 50 kinds of mineral resources are extracted from our country, their value is 3.3 trillion US dollars. In addition, two-thirds of machine-building products produced in the region are produced in Uzbekistan[4]. In the following years, attention is being paid to increase the possibilities in this regard. In particular, in the third priority direction of the action strategy for the development of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, the development and liberalization of the economy is indicated as a priority task[5]. This also serves to further increase the economic opportunities and development of Uzbekistan.

Due to the specific narrowness of the borders of the countries of the Central Asian region, recent changes, and the fact that the same natural-geographical environment is divided into different parts, it is seen that the population located in it is extremely dense near certain borders and extremely sparse near certain borders. This causes a large population to gather near the borders with a favorable natural-geographical environment and decrease the tolerance of the natural-geographical environment, and the level of the natural-geographical environment to feed the population of this place decreases.

In historical times, the nature of the relationship between man and nature was often associated with the social system.

Capitalist relations are described from a negative point of view, that is, they are believed to lead to increased impacts on nature, its impoverishment, and a number of environmental

problems. But one should not forget that the geographical factor and natural conditions play an important role in the formation of society and its life. The geographical factor is the main condition of human material life, it indirectly affects the character (property) of the social system through the method of production of material wealth [6]. For this reason, taking into account the large demographic burden of the population of Central Asia, it will be necessary to clarify the regional problems of population settlement between the countries and to develop long-term demo-ecological programs-goals.

In today's active demographic situation, it is necessary to make a deep analysis of the changes in the location of the population. Despite the fact that the establishment of new settlements is carried out on the basis of program-targeted plans at the state level, the fact that settlements lead to changes in natural-geographical conditions in the next 20-30 years may cause big problems. At the regional scale, most of the settlements are located in areas where living is very comfortable and convenient or in favorable natural and geographical conditions.

The regular increase in the number of the population causes an increase in the number and area of settlements and a decrease in favorable natural-geographical areas. This situation affects the degradation of landscapes, the ecological balance and the lifestyle of the population. Taking into account the specific characteristics of each region, it is necessary to determine the amount of demographic load, to standardize it, and to improve the scientific basis of rational territorial organization of settlements.

According to UN forecasts, the population of Central Asia will reach 94.2 million people by 2050.

- Uzbekistan - 41 million;
- Kazakhstan - 23 million;
- Tajikistan - 13.5 million;
- Kyrgyzstan - 8.1 million;
- Turkmenistan - 7.8 million[7].

The native population of Uzbekistan is made up of Uzbeks. Also, representatives of more than 130 nationalities and peoples live in our country, such as Karakalpaks, Tajiks, Kazakhs, Kyrgyz, Turkmen, Tatars, Crimean Tatars, Azerbaijanis, Bashkirs, Slavs. All conditions have been created so that their national rights and customs are not discriminated against. Teaching in seven languages is introduced in schools, the principle of social justice is followed in matters of selection and placement of personnel, distribution of culture and spiritual wealth. Newspapers, books, textbooks, training manuals and other literature are published in seven languages. Television broadcasts and radio broadcasts have been launched to meet the needs of many nations. Representatives of other nationalities are widely involved in state and public affairs.

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